

Compare Pre-Dosing with Midazolam (Co-Induction) Versus Pre-Dosing with Propofol (Auto Co-Induction), using Priming Principle on Requirement of Propofol as Inducing Agent and Hemodynamic Stability, in Patients Posted for Brain Biopsy Surgeries

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Abstract:

Background: "Co-induction refers to the simultaneous administration of more than one drug that enhance the process of inducing anaesthesia, resulting in a synergistic effect. "Auto-co-induction" refers to the practice of administering a predetermined amount of an induction agent before administering a full dosage of the same agent. This approach is sometimes referred to as "the priming technique". Our study aimed to compare effect of propofol priming and midazolam pre-dosing on demand of total induction dose of propofol and peri-intubation hemodynamics.

Method: Total 105 patients of ASA grade I & II, aged 18-65 years were registered to this study and divided into three groups: Group P (Propofol), M (Midazolam) and N (Normal Saline). 1mcg/kg, Inj. Fentanyl was injected to all patients, 5 minutes prior to the induction and preoxygenated with 100% oxygen. The study group P received priming dose of Propofol 0.5 mg/kg, study group M received Midazolam 0.05mg/kg and study group N received Normal Saline 3ml followed by inj. 1% Propofol, at the rate of 30 mg/10 seconds till the loss of verbal command. Inj. Succinylcholine (2mg /kg) was given and appropriate size endotracheal-tube is used for intubation. No surgical stimuli were applied during 5 min after intubation. The values recorded: Total dose of propofol required, Heart Rate, Systolic BP, Diastolic BP, Mean BP and pulse-oximetry (SpO₂) measured before induction, after induction, immediately after intubation and 5 min after the intubation. Further anaesthesia was maintained on O₂ / N₂O (35% / 65%), inhalational agent isoflurane and Inj. Vecuronium. Following surgery, patients were extubated after reversing with Inj. Neostigmine and Inj. Glycopyrrolate.

Statistical analysis: Analysed with the help of SPSS 20 software for windows. Appropriate univariate and bivariate analysis and ANOVA for comparing more than two means will be carried out and use of Student's t-test and χ^2 test for categorical data will be applied to check the hypothesis according to the type of data i.e. continuous and categorical.

Result: All three groups were similar regarding age, weight, sex, ASA status, baseline vitals. The mean total dose requirement of propofol was 69.2+12.3 mg in group M, 136.9+27.4 mg in group N and 89.5+18.7 mg in group P. The value showed statistically significant difference among the groups. The least requirement of propofol was seen in group M and maximum in group N. No statistically significant difference was seen among group in SBP, DBP and MAP, 5 minutes after intubation.

Conclusion: Midazolam Pre-dosing (co-induction) was found better than pre-dosing with propofol (auto-coinduction) as far as demand of induction dose of propofol and cardiovascular stability were concerned, although delayed recovery and discharge to home due to sedation in day care surgeries were seen.

Keywords: Co-induction; Auto-coinduction; Propofol; Midazolam.

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Introduction

Intravenous induction of general anaesthesia is associated with number of alterations in hemodynamics and physiology of various body systems. [1] Propofol has been established as an excellent intravenous anaesthetic agent for

induction because of its fast onset, short duration of action, clear-headed recovery [2], providing better intubating conditions, and minimal postoperative complications. However, rapid IV injection of propofol is associated with dose dependent fall in

the blood pressure [3]. Concurrent use of nitrous oxide, opioids, barbiturate i.e. midazolam, using local or regional anaesthesia, use of priming principle; co-induction several methods have been tried to reduce dose requirement of induction agent. [4,5]

Materials and Method:

After obtaining approval from institutional ethics committee, this Prospective Randomised Double Blind study was conducted on 105, PAC fit, ASA Grade I & II patients, undergoing elective brain biopsy surgery. Following the acquisition of written informed permission from all participants, the patients were randomly allocated into three groups of similar size (N=35). Group P received propofol, Group M received midazolam, and Group N received normal saline.

The allocation of these groups was determined using the sealed envelope approach, which was marked with numerical codes. The anaesthetic staff who administered the drugs was not involved in the study. On the day of surgery, patients were wheeled to Operation theatre. The patients were preloaded with 10 ml/kg of crystalloids. Multipara monitors were connected and baseline Systolic (SBP), Diastolic (DBP) and Mean arterial pressure (MAP), Heart rate (HR) and SpO₂ were recorded. All the patients were pre-medicated with inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.004mg/kg. Preoxygenation with 100% oxygen was started. 5 minutes after Inj. Fentanyl 2mcg/kg, the group P received priming dose of Propofol 0.5 mg/kg, group M received Midazolam 0.05mg/kg and group N received

Normal Saline 3ml. The research medicines were produced by an independent anaesthesiologist who was not involved in the investigation.

The syringe was covered with opaque paper wrapping. Following a 1-minute period of administering the study medication, all patients were then given 1% propofol at a rate of 30 mg/10 seconds until they reached a state where they could no longer respond to verbal commands.

Endotracheal intubation was performed following the administration of Inj. succinylcholine (2mg/kg) using an ET tube of suitable size. No surgical stimuli were applied during 5 minutes post-intubation. Further anaesthesia was maintained on O₂ / N₂O (35% / 65%), inhalational agent isoflurane and Inj. Vecuronium 0.1 mg/kg as loading dose & then 0.01 mg/kg as per the requirement. After surgery all the patients were reversed with Inj. Neostigmine and Inj. Glycopyrrolate.

The study examined the total dosage needed of propofol, as well as the hemodynamic parameters HR, SBP, DBP, MBP, and SpO₂ at several time points: prior induction, following induction, immediately after intubation, and 5 minutes after intubation. The study used the 5-minute mark after intubation as the completion point.

Result:

The three groups were identical regarding age, weight, sex and ASA status. There was no statistically significant difference among the groups as seen in Table no 1(A) & (B).

Table 1(A): Comparison of Mean Age and Weight of Patients among the Groups

	Group			Statistics					
	M	N	P	M Vs N		M Vs P		N Vs P	
	Mean+SD	Mean+SD	Mean+SD	T test	P value	T test	P value	T test	P value
Age	41.5+13.1	42.5+14.2	44+12.8	0.306	0.76	0.809	0.421	0.468	0.641
Weight	63.7+11.6	62.3+11.2	63+12.3	0.524	0.602	0.249	0.804	0.254	0.801

Table 1(B): Sex Wise Distribution (Chi square = 0.92; P = 0.631) & ASA Status (Chi square = 0.09; P = 0.958)

Sex	GROUPS		
	M	N	P
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Female	14 (40)	18 (51.4)	16 (45.7)
Male	21 (60)	17 (48.6)	19 (54.3)
ASA GRADE	M N(%)	N N (%)	P N (%)
I	24(68.6)	23(65.7)	23(65.7)
II	11 (31.4)	12 (34.3)	12 (34.3)

Table 2: Total Dose of Propofol (Mean)

	Group			Statistics					
	M	N	P	M Vs N		M Vs P		N Vs P	
	Mean+SD	Mean+SD	Mean+SD	T test	P value	T test	P value	T test	P value
Total Dose of Propofol	69.2+12.3	136.9+27.4	89.5+18.7	13.37	<0.0001	5.365	0.001	8.453	0.0001

In group M, the average total dosage of propofol required was 69.2±12.3 mg. In group N, the average total dose of propofol required was 136.9±27.4 mg. In group P, the average total dose of propofol required was 89.5±18.7 mg. The observed value exhibited a statistically significant disparity between the groups. (Table no. 2).

Table 3: Heart Rate Comparison

Heart Rate	Group			Statistics								
	M		N		P		M Vs N		M Vs P		N Vs P	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	T test	P value	T test	P value	T test	P value
Baseline	82.3	13.4	81.5	9.8	81.6	11.5	0.285	0.777	0.23	0.819	0.045	0.964
Before Induction	82.5	13.1	81.1	9.7	82.3	11	0.487	0.628	0.05	0.961	0.484	0.63
After Induction	85	12.8	83.2	9.8	83.7	10.8	0.639	0.525	0.081	0.936	0.612	0.542
After Intubation	89.6	12.7	95.3	9.5	84.5	10.6	2.125	0.01	1.824	0.03	4.486	0.0001
5 Minutes	81.7	13.2	81.4	9.8	80.9	11.2	0.103	0.918	0.265	0.792	0.194	0.847

Group M v/s N, showed P value 0.01 (significant), group M v/s P group showed P value 0.03 (significant) and group N v/s P group showed P value 0.0001, which was highly significant. The table above demonstrates that the increase in heart rate following intubation was highest in group N and lowest in group P.

Table 4: Systolic Blood Pressure Comparison

SBP	Group			Statistics								
	M		N		P		M Vs N		M Vs P		N Vs P	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	T test	P value	T test	P value	T test	P value
Baseline	125	15.5	126.7	13	125.5	10.7	0.494	0.623	0.153	0.879	0.422	0.674
Before Induction	123.1	14.9	126.7	12.1	118.8	10.1	1.112	0.27	1.391	0.169	2.943	0.004
After Induction	108.3	11.9	119.1	12.1	110	9.3	3.745	<0.0001	0.647	0.52	3.521	0.001
After Intubation	140.3	14.1	146.9	12.1	134.1	9.9	2.114	0.038	2.109	0.038	4.841	<0.0001
5 Minutes	124.2	14.7	125.1	12.3	123.9	9.7	0.291	0.772	0.105	0.916	0.475	0.636

(TABLE-4) After inducing with propofol, the decrease in mean SBP was clearly seen from 123.1mm of Hg to 108.3 mm of Hg in group M, from 126.7 mm of Hg to 119.1 mm of Hg in group N and from 118.8 mm of Hg to 110 mm of Hg in group P. the difference among all the groups were statistically significant (p<0.0001). No statistically significant difference was seen in mean SBP, 5 minutes after intubation.

Table 5: Mean Diastolic Blood Pressure Comparison

DBP	Group						Statistics					
	M		N		P		M Vs N		M Vs P		N Vs P	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	T test	P value	T test	P value	T test	P value
Baseline	76.3	8.8	80.0	10.1	79.7	6	1.611	0.112	1.846	0.069	0.157	0.876
Before Induction	75.0	9.1	78.5	9.9	77.6	5.8	1.518	0.134	1.39	0.169	0.471	0.639
After Induction	69.8	9.0	73.8	9.8	71.5	5.9	1.77	0.081	0.928	0.357	1.188	0.239
After Intubation	83.1	8.6	93.7	9.3	76.8	6.8	4.965	<0.0001	3.416	0.001	8.703	<0.0001
5 Minutes	76.9	8.5	80.5	10.2	78.0	6.1	1.603	0.114	0.598	0.552	1.267	0.209

As per Table-5, After intubation, on comparing group M with group N and group N with P, we found p value was <0.0001 (highly significant) though in M v/s P group P value was found significant otherwise no

statistically significant difference was seen in DBP before induction, after induction and 5 minutes after intubation.

Table 6: Mean Map Comparison

MAP	Group			Statistics					
	M	N	P	M Vs N		M Vs P		N Vs P	
	Mean+SD	Mean+SD	Mean+SD	T test	P value	T test	P value	T test	P value
Baseline	92.6+9.5	95.5+10	94.9+6.6	1.234	0.221	1.181	0.242	0.281	0.78
Before Induction	91+9.4	94.6+9.6	91.4+5.9	1.571	0.121	0.183	0.856	1.687	0.096
After Induction	82.6+8.4	88.7+9.7	84.5+6.2	2.827	0.006	1.12	0.267	2.139	0.036
After Intubation	102.3+8.6	110.5+8.9	88.8+6.7	3.949	<0.0001	7.32	<0.0001	11.546	<0.0001
5 Minutes	92.7+9.3	95.3+9.3	92+5.8	1.17	0.246	0.34	0.735	1.746	0.085

(TABLE-6) The rise in mean MAP was seen after intubation in all groups i.e. from 82.6 to 102.3 mm of Hg, 88.7 to 110.5 mm of Hg & 84.5 to 88.8 mm of Hg in group M, N and P respectively. After intubation, in group M v/s N, M vs P and group N vs P, the result was found to be highly significant with p value <0.0001.

Table 7: SpO₂ Comparison

SPO2	Group			Statistics					
	M	N	P	M Vs N		M Vs P		N Vs P	
	Mean+SD	Mean+SD	Mean+SD	T test	P value	T test	P value	T test	P value
Baseline	98.2+0.8	98+0.7	98.2+0.8	1.418	0.161	0.149	0.882	1.208	0.231
Before Induction	98.9+0.3	98.8+0.4	98.9+0.3	1.365	0.177	0	1	1.365	0.177
After Induction	99.1+0.3	99+0.2	99+0.2	1.392	0.169	1.392	0.169	0	1
After Intubation	99+0	99+0	98.9+0.3	0	1	1.785	0.079	1.785	0.079
5 Minutes	99.3+0.5	99.3+0.5	99.4+0.5	0	1	0.246	0.806	0.246	0.806

Mean plot of SpO₂ depicting, no difference in the SpO₂ was seen among the groups.

Discussion:

Brain biopsy surgeries are of small duration surgeries, requiring short acting induction agent, which gives clear headed recovery. Propofol is best fit as induction agent for day care surgeries. In order to ensure stable blood flow during the administration of propofol, several methods were employed [6]. These included the simultaneous use of N₂O, opioids, barbiturates, and benzodiazepines such as midazolam. Additionally, the use of methylene blue, esmolol, and α 2 agonists were implemented. Furthermore, local and regional anaesthesia were utilised to enhance the effects. Lastly, the coinduction: priming principle was employed. [9-13]. Studies have shown that midazolam can reduce the induction dose of propofol by up to 52%. [14] A small study on priming principle for the induction dose of propofol was conducted by Maroof et al had suggested initial administration of priming dose of propofol (25% of the total dose requirement) is believed to

induce anxiolysis and therefore minimizes the associated sympathetic drive and reduces overall induction dose of propofol. [3,15,16]. Djaiani [2] and Anderson [14] with their colleague carried out a study and concluded that combination of midazolam and propofol and propofol auto-co-induction reduces further induction dose of propofol. Similar results have shown with other studies [3,17,18] also. Anil Kumar and his colleagues [16] discovered that propofol auto-co-induction resulted in a decrease of over 25% in the amount of propofol needed for induction. The amnesic and sedative effects of propofol at dosages below the level of inducing sleep can help in achieving anaesthesia with a lesser dose of propofol for induction. [15,16,17,19] Naphade et al [22] showed a reduction of 35%, Minaxi et al [23] showed 38.26% reduction in the dose of propofol in midazolam group and 36.1% reduction in propofol group. In our investigation, we administered a priming dose of 0.5mg/kg propofol, 0.05mg/kg midazolam, and 3ml normal saline to groups P, M, and N, respectively. The induction of

propofol was considered complete when the subjects lost the ability to follow vocal commands.

After intubation, (TABLE-3) increase in HR was maximum in the N group compared to the other two groups (P 0.001). The rise in group M was significantly bigger than in group P (P=0.03) among the M and P groups. However, no difference was seen after 5 minutes after intubation. Krupali et al [24] and Kataria et al [26] achieved similar findings. This result may be observed because midazolam does not protect against increase in HR, which is expected during intubation unlike thiopentone and propofol which easily prevent compensatory rise in HR by blunting baroreceptor reflex.

When comparing the average systolic blood pressure (SBP), a decrease in the average SBP was observed after induction, and an increase was observed following intubation in all three groups (TABLE-4).

Group M had a significantly higher increase compared to group P (P=0.038). In a research conducted by Young Soo Lim et al [23], it was demonstrated that the decrease in average systolic blood pressure (SBP) was less pronounced in the group treated with midazolam-propofol compared to the control group. Anil Kumar and colleagues [3] discovered that the average systolic blood pressure (SBP) was higher in the propofol auto co-induction group after the induction phase (P = 0.0002).

On the other hand, the control group saw a greater increase in SBP after intubation (P=0.000) and 5 minutes after intubation (P=0.000). In addition, the study conducted by Kataria et al [26] demonstrated a decrease in the average systolic blood pressure (SBP) in all three groups, while the midazolam group saw a 20% rise in average SBP following intubation [23].

When comparing the average diastolic blood pressure (DBP), there was no notable difference before and after the induction in the groups. This lack of difference was statistically significant, with a p-value more than 0.05, as shown in Table 5. Following intubation, a statistically significant difference (p=0.0001) was seen in the mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) across the groups, with the lowest DBP observed in group P. In a study by Kataria et al [26] the rise in mean DBP after intubation was higher in midazolam propofol co-induction group as compared to propofol auto co-induction group [23].

In our study we found mean MAP was decreased in all groups, after induction and increase was observed after intubation in all (TABLE-6). Rise in MAP after intubation in all three groups was due to stress response produced by laryngoscopy and

endotracheal intubation. But least rise in MAP was observed in group P, which was due to reduction in the sympathetic drive, cardiac output and reduced induction dose of propofol. Propofol pre-treatment does not completely obtund reflex sympathetic drive secondary to intubation. According to research conducted by Uma Shrivastava et al [13], the average mean arterial pressure (MAP) decreased considerably in all three groups following induction. The control group exhibited a 21% rise in mean MAP following intubation. The midazolam group showed a 13% increase, the propofol group showed an 11% increase, and the ketamine group showed the smallest increase of 4%. [6] In a research conducted by WM Leong et al [27], it was shown that both the control group and the propofol auto-coinduction group saw a comparable reduction in mean arterial pressure (MAP). [26] Propofol causes fall in blood pressure by inhibiting vasomotor activity and also showing negative inotropic effect.

Conclusion:

We conclude that Midazolam co-induction is more effective as compared to propofol auto co-induction in reducing the requirement of propofol for induction of general anaesthesia. Whereas priming with propofol appears to provide more hemodynamic stability in post-induction and post intubation period when compared to midazolam pre-dosing.

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